
"YAK HERDERS ARE THE COSMIC SUN":
A MGO LOG HERDSWOMAN'S SINGING LIFE (2022)
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ABSTRACT

This text describes the singing life of Phur 'tsho (b. 1960), a herder born in the contemporary Khang sar (Kangsai) Town, Gcig sgril (Jiuzhi) County, Mgo log (Guoluo) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. Phur 'tsho learned songs from her mother, friends, and the radio. She sang while herding calves and yaks with her herdmates. She moved to a new home in Smin thang (Mentang) Township after her mother and maternal uncle arranged her marriage in 1976.

KEYWORDS

Tibetan women singing, Himalayan pastoral songs, Golok yak-hair tent, Qinghai herdswomen songs

Mountaintops shrouded in clouds pierced the sky on the horizon. An eagle searching for food soared above yaks, horses, and sheep, calmly grazing on the banks of a creek that twisted and turned through the grassland like a dragon.

Three riders on two yaks passed by a thawing lake. Phur 'tsho sat behind her mother on a polled, black yak. Phur 'tsho's aunt rode a brown yak. Phur 'tsho tapped her mother's back from the discomfort caused by sitting on the yak's spine. Phur 'tsho's mother ignored her and began singing as they rode by grazing yaks that looked up in surprise, their ears twitching, grass stems hanging from their mouths, and watching and listening, mesmerized by a piercingly sharp melody that seemed to reach the ends of the earth and somehow, for a short time, seemed to answer all the problems any sentient creature was capable of having.

Phur 'tsho forgot her discomfort and wrapped her arms

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around her mother. She leaned her head against her mother's back and announced, "Mom! I want to be a singer just like you!" when the song ended.

Her aunt smiled and looked at Phur 'tsho, who smiled back.

FAMILY AND CHILDHOOD LIFE

Phur 'tsho (b. 1964) was born in the Hor skor (Huoerguo) Tribe, Khang sar (Kangsai) Township, Gcig sgril (Jiuzhi) County, Mgo log (Guoluo) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. Phur 'tsho's mother, Bo gces (b. 1923-2021), was the mother of four sons (Sran mgo, b. 1951; Zla po, 1953-2019; 'Jam mgon, b. 1955; and 'Tshogs po, b. 1957-2022) and three daughters (Phur 'tsho; Ma 'jug, b. 1966; and 'Da' mo, b. 1970). Phur 'tsho was her fifth child. Her father passed away in 1965.

During Phur 'tsho's childhood, Hor skor Dus chung¹ consisted of about ten households, two leaders, and an accountant who organized the brigade, offering jobs to brigade members over fifteen. All local families lived in yak-hair tents. Phur 'tsho's family lived in a small tent inherited from Bo gces' parents. Men herded yaks, sheep, and horses, while women milked and produced dairy products. From May to September, Bo gces milked twice daily and made butter and other dairy products.

Leaders visited each household, taking from each family a quota of dairy products and livestock each was required to produce. Households were given yaks and sheep to slaughter to provide meat and dairy products. The amount depended on household size. A family of six was given three yaks and three sheep (one yak and one sheep per two family members). Locals typically slaughtered yaks in the eleventh lunar month and sheep in the sixth or seventh lunar month.

The leaders and accountant were responsible for selling brigade livestock and dairy products in Gcig sgril County Town.

¹ CT=Colloquial Tibetan; LT=Literary Tibetan. CT: *dus chung* (LT: *ru chung*) = Ch: *xiaodui* 'small brigade' 'production team'. Communes consisted of *ru chen* 'big brigades' that were further divided into *dus chung*. Hereafter, I use "brigade" for *dus chung*.

They were accompanied by two or three young male brigade members who helped herd the livestock to the government slaughterhouse, where a Muslim butcher was paid to kill the animals.

The slaughterhouse paid thirty RMB each for big yaks and fifteen RMB each for small yaks and sheep. The sellers skinned the dead animals.

Cheese and butter were sold to the County Town Bureau of Livestock Husbandry. One kilogram of butter sold for one to two RMB, and one kilogram of cheese sold for four to eight RMB. The sales value was paid to each brigade household after deducting the meat and dairy products that had earlier been allocated to each household.

Phur 'tsho's family had four neighbors who were relatives, including her maternal uncle's (Don grub, 1931-1990) family. The four families mutually assisted each other, and the families' children often played and herded yak calves together.

Bo gces was responsible for milking twenty yaks and helped a neighbor milk the twenty yaks she had been assigned. Bo gces' family was not responsible for herding sheep.

Her son, Zla po, herded twenty yaks while her oldest son, Sran mgo, was a tractor driver for Khang sar Township and transported goods. Phur 'tsho helped the youngest son, 'Tshogs po, herd calves and yaks.

Bo gces, Zla po, and Sran mgo each received 0.10 RMB per day as payment for their work. Phur 'tsho and her other siblings were under fifteen and had no jobs.

'Jam mgon was given to his maternal aunt, who could not give birth. He herded yak calves for his adopted family.

Locals wore sheepskin robes and leather boots. Bo gces would bury dried yak skins. Unearth them when they were soft, cut the leather into pieces of appropriate size and shape, and sew them together with yak leather string using an awl and needle to make boots for her children.

Don grub herded sheep. He kept the skin of sheep killed by wolves and those that had died from illness and sewed the skins into robes for his children and Phur 'tsho's children.

Phur 'tsho's family's main food was roasted barley flour, butter, cheese, milk, and yogurt. Bo gces roasted barley in a metal pot on the adobe stove and ground it with a stone mill.

Sran mgo bought items such as barley, flour, salt, pots, scoops, bowls, long underwear, shirts, and scarves at the township town for his family from his family's salary.

HERDING LIFE

At seven, Phur 'tsho cared for her younger sisters and helped her mother fetch water, collect yak dung for fuel, and cook. Sometimes, she herded her family's calves with 'Tshogs po and neighboring children who also herded their families' calves. Phur 'tsho played with her herding mates, who sang while they herded together. This motivated Phur 'tsho to learn some songs, so Bo gces taught her to sing in return for her fetching water and herding calves. Phur 'tsho was passionate about learning new songs and also learned songs from neighboring older female relatives.

Phur 'tsho's friends would ask Bo gces to allow Phur 'tsho to spend the night at their home, and Bo gces typically agreed. Phur 'tsho enjoyed spending nights at her friends' tents because she could learn new songs while listening to elders sing in the tents.

Phur 'tsho learned this herding song from older women during these years.

TEXT AS PERFORMED

¹ནོར་ལ་ནག་ཚུང་ཇ་མགོའི་ཟེལ་བ་རེད།

²འདིའི་ལ་ནོར་རྩེ་འཇམ་གླིང་ཉེ་མ་རེད།

³ལྷག་ལ་ལག་ག་ནམ་མཁའི་སྐར་མ་རེད།

⁴འདིའི་ལ་ལྷག་རྩེ་བཙོ་ལྡེའི་དུང་ལྷ་རེད།

⁵རྟ་ལ་འདོ་བ་མཚོ་ཁའི་མེ་རྟོག་རེད།

⁶འདིའི་ལ་རྟ་རྩེ་མཚོ་ནང་ནོར་བུ་རེད།

LITERARY POETIC TEXT

¹མོར་ནག་ཚུང་རྩ་མགོའི་བེལ་བ་རེད།

²དེའི་མོར་རྩི་འཇམ་གླིང་ཉི་མ་རེད།

³ལྷག་ལག་ག་ནམ་མཁའི་སྐར་མ་རེད།

⁴དེའི་ལྷག་རྩི་བཙོ་ཡའི་དུང་རྩ་རེད།

⁵རྟ་འདྲ་བ་མཚོ་ལའི་མེ་ཉྟག་རེད།

⁶དེའི་རྟ་རྩི་མཚོ་ནང་མོར་བུ་རེད།

ENGLISH TRANSLATION

¹Black yaks are dew on mountain peaks' grassy tops

²Yak herders are the cosmic sun

³Yearlings are glittering stars in the sky

⁴Shepherds are the milky full moon

⁵Horses are colorful flowers on the lake banks

⁶Horse-herders are the lake's inner jewel

In 1972, Zla po bought a rectangular black radio from the County Town, and the family listened to news and songs broadcast by the Mtsho sngon Tibetan Radio Station. Phur 'tsho and her siblings listened to a radio broadcast each night at nine PM. She was only interested in the singing part of the broadcast when different singers sang various songs. Songs that had been broadcast earlier were sometimes rebroadcast.

Zla po slept alone in a small sod-brick room covered with willow branches near the family tent and would take the radio with him when he went to bed. If he went to bed early, Phur 'tsho would ask Zla po to loan her his radio so she could listen to songs, and he usually agreed. Phur 'tsho would put the radio next to her pillow and listen. News bored her, but she forced herself to listen, fearful of missing the songs. She turned off the radio a few times when boredom set in and then discovered she had missed the singing part once she turned the radio back on. Her family had no watches or clocks, so it was easy to miss a set time.

She learned this song from listening to the radio.

TEXT AS PERFORMED

¹འདིའི་ནི་རྩ་མགོ་རི་མགོ་སྐྱན་ལྷུ་མ་རེད།

²དྲི་ནི་ཞེས་པོ་ལ་ཆེད་ར་གུར་ཀྱམ་རེད།

³འདིའི་ནི་རྩ་སྐད་རི་སྐད་མེ་ཏྲོག་རེད།

⁴སྐྱེ་ནི་ཡག་པ་མེ་ཏྲོག་ལེར་ཆེན་རེད།

⁵འདིའི་ནི་རྩ་ཞོལ་རི་ཞོལ་ཆུ་འགོ་རེད།

⁶ཆུ་ནི་ཡག་པ་འཛམ་གླིང་གསོལ་ཆུ་རེད།

LITERARY POETIC TEXT

¹འདིའི་རྩ་མགོ་རི་མགོ་སྐྱན་ལྷུ་མ་རེད།

²དྲི་ཞེས་པོ་ལ་ཆེད་ར་གུར་ཀྱམ་རེད།

³འདིའི་རྩ་སྐད་རི་སྐད་མེ་ཏྲོག་རེད།

⁴སྐྱེས་ཡག་པ་མེ་ཏྲོག་ལེར་ཆེན་རེད།

⁵འདིའི་རྩ་ཞོལ་རི་ཞོལ་ཆུ་འགོ་རེད།

⁶ཆུ་ནི་ཡག་པ་འཛམ་གླིང་འབྲུང་ཆུ་རེད།

ENGLISH TRANSLATION

¹Medicinal herbs cover mountaintops

²Kha che's saffron emits fragrant perfume

³Various flowers bloom on mountain-sides

⁴The marsh marigold is the most beautiful

⁵The mountain foot is rich with springs

⁶The cleanest spring – drinking water for the universe

A MISSING RADIO

Zla po could read and write Tibetan and had basic math knowledge, so he became the tribe accountant in about 1974. He calculated each worker's annual salary and recorded each female worker's dairy products. Each year, the tribe leaders and the accountant calculated the amount of dairy products the tribe produced and sold annually and divided the unsold dairy products among brigade members. He wrote a receipt for each family. Each family's head or a family member could take the receipt and get the allocation from the home of a leader who temporarily stored dairy products in their homes.

Once, Zla po's friend, Nyi ma, came to see him to get the receipt for his family. They chatted in the sod-brick room and listened to the radio. Later, Zla po invited his friend to his family tent for a meal. Afterward, feeling tired, Zla po took a short nap. He invited Nyi ma to spend the night at his home, but Nyi ma said he had to return home.

The next day Zla po discovered his radio was missing and also discovered Nyi ma's footprints near the door of his room. Convinced his friend had stolen the radio, he rode a horse to Nyi ma's family, dismounted, and called Nyi ma, who soon came and assured him he had not stolen the radio. Zla po was embarrassed when his friend swore he had not stolen the radio. He trusted Nyi ma and apologized. Nyi ma forgave him and invited him to his home.

The following day, while herding calves, 'Tshogs po opened a bag he discovered in a marmot burrow and found Zla po's radio and a piece of paper. He couldn't read, so he didn't know what was written on the paper. That night, he gave Zla po the bag and paper. Zla po recognized the paper as the receipt for Nyi ma's family he had written two days earlier. He angrily believed he had been lied to and wanted revenge. However, Nyi ma's uncle, Zla po's friend, apologized on behalf of Nyi ma, so he forgave Nyi ma.

Phur 'tsho was delighted with the radio's return and resumed listening to the radio every night, learning more songs. She never forgot that time of the missing radio because she had heard no songs for two days and had been terribly dejected.

MARRIAGE

Bo gces and one of her cousins arranged a marriage for Phur 'tsho when she turned seventeen. Bo gces asked another cousin to consult a local high-ranking *bla ma* to divine the marriage's suitability. The *bla ma* pronounced it was a good marriage, and Phur 'tsho would have a happy life. Bo gces then agreed to the marriage. Phur 'tsho, like other girls, followed her mother and uncle's suggestion.

On an auspicious day, Phur 'tsho wore the outfit her mother had given her: a new sheepskin robe and a silver belt inlaid with coral. Phur 'tsho and Zla po then rode horses to her future husband's home. Looking back at her home Phur 'tsho saw Bo gces watching them leave.

In 2022, Phur 'tsho occasionally sang when she herded and searched for missing yaks.

TIBETAN TERMS

'jam mgon འཇམ་མགོན།

'tshogs po འཚོགས་པོ།

bo gces བོ་གཅེས།

bun khrang བུན་ཁང་།

don grub དོན་གུབ།

dus chung དུས་ཚུང་། (CT)

hor skor ཧོར་སྐོར།

gcig sgril གཅིག་སྒྲིལ།

golok, mgo log མགོ་ལོག།

gu ru 'phrin las ལུ་རུ་འཕྲིན་ལས།

khang sar ཁང་སར།

mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྔོན།

nyi ma ཉེ་མ།

phur 'tsho ཕུར་འཚོ།

ru chen རུ་ཚེན།

ru chung རུ་ཚུང་།

sran mgo སྐར་མགོ།

zla po ཟླ་པོ།

CHINESE TERMS

Gerichengli 格日成立

Guoluo 果洛

Huoerguo 霍尔果

Jiuzhi 久治

Kangsai 康赛

Qinghai 青海